

Occurrence of Desrhamnosylverbascoside in *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* and NMR Studies of its Acetate

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We have reported earlier many new iridoids from the seeds and leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*¹. Rathore *et al.* also reported few new iridoids from the plant². Recently we have isolated a new phenylpropanoid glycoside nycoside A from its seeds³. In this communication we report the isolation of another phenylpropanoid glucoside (**1**) from the leaves.

1: R = R₁ = H

2: R = R₁ = Ac

3: R = H, R₁ = Xylose

Results and Discussion

Ethyl acetate and butanol soluble fractions from methanol extract on repeated chromatography over silica gel yielded an amorphous powder (**1**), C₂₃H₂₆O₁₁. Acetylation of **1** with NaOAc and Ac₂O afforded a heptaacetate (**2**). Preliminary examination of the spectral data of the heptaacetate indicated it to be a phenylpropanoid glucoside. The ¹H nmr spectrum of **2** showed doublets at δ 6.20 and 7.51 (d each, *J* 16 Hz) for *trans*-olefinic protons of the caffeoyl group and a triplet at δ 5.11 assignable to the ester-bearing methine proton, which shows that the caffeoyl

group is linked to the C-4' hydroxyl group of glucose. The multiplets at δ 2.71–2.86 (br m, 2H- β), 3.61 and 4.06 (m each, 2H- α) could be assigned to the methylene protons of the 3,4-diacetoxyphenylethyl ether moiety in **2**. The anomeric proton of glucose appeared as a doublet at δ 4.43 (*J* 8 Hz) showing the glucose linkage as β . Six aromatic protons occurred in the region δ 6.9–7.29. Comparison of the ¹H and ¹³C nmr data of **2** with those of nonacetate of nycoside A (**3**) isolated earlier from the seeds of this plant showed that **1** was identical with nycoside A except for the absence of xylose unit in **1**. Thus compound **1** is desrhamnosylverbascoside. The structure assigned to compound **1** was further confirmed by proton decoupling studies on its heptaacetate.

Irradiation of the C β -methylene protons resulted in the collapse of the multiplets at δ 3.61 and 4.06 into doublets (*J* 9.5 Hz). Irradiation of either of the olefinic doublets at δ 6.20 and 7.51 caused the collapse of the other doublet into a singlet. When the anomeric proton at δ 4.43 was irradiated, the double doublet at δ 4.92 (H-2') changed to a doublet (*J* 9.3 Hz). Irradiation of the double doublet at δ 4.92 (H-2') and triplet at δ 5.18 (H-3') caused the collapse of the doublet at δ 4.43 (H-1') into a singlet and the double doublet at δ 4.92 into a doublet respectively. When the triplet at δ 5.11 (H-4') was irradiated there was

TABLE-1 NMR DATA OF DESRHAMNOSYLVERBASCOSIDE HEPTAACETATE

Carbon/ Proton no.	¹³ C nmr shift* in ppm (multiplicity in APT)	¹ H nmr shift** (ppm)	Multiplicity (J Hz)	Decoupling information	
				Changed to (J Hz)	on irradiation of
1'	100.73	4.43	d(8.0)	s	H-2'
2'	72.73	4.92	dd(8.0, 9.3)	d(9.3)	H-1'
				d(8.0)	H-3'
3'	71.38	5.18	t(9.3)	d(9.3)	H-2'
4'	69.11	5.11	t(9.3)	d(9.3)	H-3'
				d(9.3)	H-5'
5'	72.03	3.67	m	d(9.3)	H-6'
				simplified	H-4'
6'	62.36	4.08	m	AB pattern	H-5'
		4.19		(12.3)	
α	69.82	4.06	1H,m	d(9.5)	H-β _{1,β2}
		3.61	1H,m	d(9.5)	
β	35.35	2.71-2.86	2H,m	-	-
1	137.34	-	-	-	-
2	123.73	6.93-6.98 ^a	m	-	-
3	141.94	-	-	-	-
4	140.67	-	-	-	-
5	122.90	6.93-6.98 ^a	m	-	-
6	126.97	-	-	-	-
-CO-	164.83	-	-	-	-
α'	117.68	6.20	d(16.0)	s	H-β'
β'	144.53	7.51	d(16.0)	s	H-α'
1''	132.75	-	-	-	-
2''	123.92	7.25	d(2.0)	s	H-6''
3''	142.60	-	-	-	-
4''	143.97	-	-	-	-
5''	123.07	7.13	d(8.3)	s	H-6''
6''	126.44	7.29	dd(2.0,8.3)	d(2.0)	H-5''
				d(8.3)	H-2''

^aThree protons overlapped to give a multiplet at δ 6.93-6.98.

*Additional carbon signals from seven OAc groups appeared at δ 20.56 and 20.43 (7×Me), 167.59, 167.71, 168.02, 169.20 (2×CO) 169.96 and 170.35. **Acetoxy protons from seven OAc groups appeared at δ 1.98, 1.84, 1.86, 2.17, 2.18, 2.19 and 2.20.

simplification of the multiplet at δ 3.67. Irradiation of the multiplet at δ 3.67 (H-5') resulted in the collapse of the triplet at δ 5.11 to a doublet and the C₆-methylene protons to an AB system (J 12.3 Hz). When the C₆-methylene was irradiated the multiplet at δ 3.67 changed to a doublet (J 9.3 Hz). These confirmed the ¹H nmr assignments of the sugar protons and also established that all the sugar ring-protons were axial, since the coupling constants varied from 8.0 to 9.5 Hz. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data and the irradiation results (Table 1) are reported for the first time for the heptaacetate of desrhamnosylverbascoside. Earlier desrhamnosyl verbascoside was

isolated from *Calceolaria hypericina* but was designated as calceolarioside A⁴. This is the first report of isolation of desrhamnosylverbascoside in Oleaceae and in the genus *Nyctanthes*. The isolation of nyctoside A and desrhamnosylverbascoside along with iridoids from *N. arbor-tristis* gives further support to the view that iridoids and phenylpropanoids co-exist in plants belonging to the family Oleaceae

Experimental

¹H nmr (300.13 MHz) and ¹³C nmr (75.46 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker AM 300L spectrometer in CDCl₃ at the Centre of

Advanced Studies Facility. The leaves of *N. arbor-tristis* were collected from Madras in August, 1991. A voucher specimen has been deposited at the herbarium of CSMDRIA, Madras, under the registry no. 701.

Isolation : Coarsely powdered leaves (2 kg) were defatted with n-hexane and then extracted with MeOH in the cold. The MeOH extract was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, treated with H₂O and extracted with Et₂O, EtOAc and n-BuOH. Compound **1** was isolated from EtOAc and n-BuOH soluble fractions by chromatography over a column of silica gel. The EtOAc-CHCl₃ (9 : 1) eluate yielded a gum which was purified by rechromatography over silica gel when compound **1** was obtained as an amorphous powder (300 mg). This was converted to its acetate and characterised as such.

Acetylation of compound 1 : Compound **1** (150 mg) was refluxed with Ac₂O (3 ml) and freshly fused NaOAc in an oil-bath for 4 h. Work-up in the usual way afforded a gummy mass which was crystallised from aqueous alcohol to give the heptaacetate (**2**; 120 mg), C₃₇H₄₀O₁₈ (from APT and NMR).

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